

The Impact of Demonetization on Indian Economy for a selected period of study from 1960 to 2022

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Abstract

On 19th May 2023, RBI declared the withdrawal of Rs. 2,000 notes as a part of its 'clean note' policy. People had time till 30th September 2023 to exchange such notes at banks or designated RBI offices.¹ The RBI governor stated that the impact of withdrawal of 2000 rupees notes will be "very very marginal" on the economy because it accounts for only 10.8% of currency in circulation. In this regard, this paper is intended to address the impact of demonetization on Indian Economy. For the study, the percentage change in the GDP growth and 5 year moving averages have been studied to understand the impact on it.

Keywords: Demonetization, Economy, GDP, Impact, RBI.

1. Introduction:

The announcement of demonetization in India is not new. Earlier it was happened four times. this is the 5th time in the country's history that the Central Bank has taken such a measure. The Section 26(2) of the RBI Act, 1934, legalizes the demonetization in India. Thorough this section, any series of banknotes can be ceased by notifying in the official gazette, by the central government with the recommendation of RBI. In spite of several petitions filed in various counts, the Supreme Court supports the demonetization is valid. The benefit of demonetization must be significant enough for the growth of GDP, digital transactions, control of inflation etc.

2. History of Demonetization:

The first attempt of demonetization was by USA in the year 1873 to remove silver and that led to economic depression for consecutive 5 years, but in the year 1969, the banking system was developed. Gana in the year 1982, Nigeria in the year 1984, Myanmar in the year 1987 experimented the demonetization in their respective countries and failed.

In India, the demonetization was announced 5 times, in the years 1946, 1978, 2014, 2016 and 2023. The aim of the respective actions have been mentioned as follows:

Year	Withdrawal of currency notes (in Rs)	Aim
1946	500,1000 and 10,000 notes	To curb the increasing black-market operations, which was a result of WW2.
1978	1000, 5000 and 10,000 notes	To attack the Counterfeit money circulating in the Indian market.
2014	All the currency issued before 2005	Notes before 2005 had very few security measures compared to those issued after that year.
2016	500, 1000 notes	To curb black money and stop counterfeit and illicit cash being used for funding terrorist activities.
2023	2000 from circulation	As a part of its 'clean note' policy

Demonetization had both negative and positive impacts in countries like . However, On the other hand, beyond the aim of introducing the demonetization, various negative impacts were seen. There was a dip in the GDP. There was less liquidity due to which the less cash flows in the markets.

2. Research Methodology:

This research paper on “The Impact of Demonetization on Indian Economy” is to understand the impact of demonetization on the Indian Economy for the selected period.

The comparative analysis of percentage change in the GDP of before and after demonetization periods of 1978, 2014 and 2016 have been considered to analyse the impact on the economy.

Along with the percentage change in the GDP, 5 year moving averages also have been studied for better understanding on the impact of the Indian Economy.

3.1. Data Collection analysis:

To understand the impact on Economy, the GDP value (in BnUS\$) from 1960 to 2023 is taken for the study.

Percentage change in the GDP is measured and compared with the similar time period from before demonetization and after demonetization is studied.

3.1.1. Nominal GDP per capita.

The below figure expresses the Nominal GDP per capita from the year 1960 to 2022. There is an upward trend in the growth.

Fig 1: Graphical representation of nominal GDP per capita from 1960-2022

Source: World bank data catalogue

3.1.2. Comparative of GDP per capital of India with the other countries in the year (2021):

Fig 2: Graphical representation of comparison of GDP of India with other countries in the year 2021

Gross domestic product per capita: other countries (2021)

Source: World bank data catalog

India is having lowest GDP per capital in comparison with the other countries like Egypt, Peru, France, Canada and USA.

3.1.3. Percentage change in the GDP:

Table 1: Percentage change in the growth of GDP from 1961 to 1996

S. No	Year (Series 1)	Before 1978 Demonetization	Year (Series 2)	After 1978 Demonetization
1	1961	3.61	1979	9.20
2	1962	5.00	1980	18.67

3	1963	11.85	1981	1.50
4	1964	13.86	1982	1.48
5	1965	3.48	1983	6.55
6	1966	-24.54	1984	-5.12
7	1967	6.90	1985	7.19
8	1968	3.65	1986	4.70
9	1969	7.54	1987	9.62
10	1970	4.67	1988	4.09
11	1971	5.36	1989	-2.53
12	1972	4.24	1990	6.34
13	1973	16.26	1991	-17.62
14	1974	13.99	1992	4.61
15	1975	-3.07	1993	-5.03
16	1976	1.90	1994	14.57
17	1977	15.53	1995	8.09
18	1978	10.75	1996	6.95

Source: World bank data catalog

- The above table represents the the percentage change in the growth of GDP from the year 1960 to 1996. It also represents the comparative analysis of impact on GDP before demonetization and after demonetization of the year 1978.
- Before demonetization of 1978 figures give that, the highest percentage of change in the GDP growth recorded at 16.26 (from the year 1972 to 1973) and the least is recorded at -24.54 (from the year 1965 to 1966). This may be due to war between India and Pakistan in the year 1965.
- After 1978 Demonetization, The highest growth recorded at 14.57 (from the year 1993 to 1994) which is -1.69 comparatively the before demonetization. The least growth was recorded in the year 1991 comparatively with 1990, I.e. -17.62%.
- So, this table clearly states that, the demonetization does not have much positive impact on the GDP.

Fig 3: Graphical representation of percentage change in the nominal GDP per capital before and after 1978 demonetization

Source: Analysis of the Table 1

- Series 1 is the period of before demonetization of the year 1978 and Series 2 represents the period after the year 1978. 18 years of data before and after 1978 has been compared and plotted on line graph to observe the changes in the GDP growth. From the above graph, out of 18 years, only 6 years data was showing higher growth than the before demonetization period. Rest of the 12 years, the growth was recorded lower than the before period.

Table 2: Percentage change in the growth of GDP from 1999 to 2014

S. No.	Year	Before 2006 Demonetization	Year	After 2006 Demonetization
1	1999	6.78	2007	27.18
2	2000	0.23	2008	-2.55
3	2001	1.81	2009	10.66
4	2002	4.22	2010	22.73
5	2003	15.99	2011	7.41
6	2004	14.71	2012	-1.38
7	2005	13.94	2013	0.70
8	2006	12.80	2014	8.30

Source: World bank data catalog

- The above table represents the the percentage change in the growth of GDP from the year 1999 to 2014. It also represents the comparative analysis of impact on GDP before demonetization and after demonetization of the year 2006.
- Before demonetization of 2006 figures give that, the highest percentage of change in the GDP growth recorded at 15.99 (from the year 2002 to 2003) and the least is recorded as 0.23 (from the year 1999 to 2000).
- After2006 Demonetization, The highest growth recorded at 27.18 (from the year 2006 to 2007) which is 11.19% more comparatively the before demonetization. The least growth was recorded in the year 2008 comparatively with the year 2007, I.e. -2.55%. This indicates that the growth in 2007 is not stable and shown the effect in the immediate consecutive year.
- Also, there was a stead down fall in the GDP growth during the period 1999-2006 but there was a high volatility found the in the growth of GDP in the later period of demonetization in the year 2006.
- So, this period also clearly states that, the demonetization does not have much positive impact on the GDP.

Fig 4: Graphical representation of percentage change in the nominal GDP per capital before and after 2006 demonetization

Source: Analysis of the Table 2

- This graph compares the 16 years of data of percentage change in the GDP during the period 1999 to 2014, I.e. the 6 years of data before and after 2006 demonitization has been compared and plotted on line graph to observe the changes in the GDP growth. From the above graph, out of 6 years, only 2 years data was showing higher growth than the before demonitization period. Rest of the 6 years, the growth was recorded lower than the before period.

Table 3: Percentage change in the growth of GDP from 2006 to 2022

S. No.	Year	Before 2014 Demonitization	Year	After 2014 Demonitization
1	2006	12.8	2015	1.92
2	2007	27.2	2016	7.55
3	2008	-2.5	2017	14.62
4	2009	10.7	2018	0.51
5	2010	22.7	2019	4.06
6	2011	7.4	2020	-6.83
7	2012	-1.4	2021	17.28
8	2013	0.7	2022	6.65
9	2014	8.3		

Source: World bank data catalog

- The above table represents the the percentage change in the growth of GDP from the year 2006 to 2022. It also represents the comparative analysis of impact on GDP before demonitization and after demonitization of the year 2014.
- Before demonitization of 2014 figures give that, the highest percentage of change in the GDP growth recorded at 27.2 (from the year 2006 to 2007) and the least is recorded as -2.5 (from the year 2007 to 2008).
- After 2014 Demonitization, The highest growth recorded at 17.28 (from the year 2020 to 2021) which is around 10% less comparatively the before demonitization. The least growth was recorded in the year 2020 comparatively with the year 2019,

I.e. -6.83%, which is 4.4% more than the earlier period of demonetization. Both periods found volatile in the growth of GDP. There is a possibility of other internal and external factors impacting the GDP growth.

- So, this period also clearly states that, the demonetization does not have much positive impact on the GDP

Fig5: Graphical representation of percentage change in the nominal GDP per capital before and after 2014 demonetization

Source: Analysis of the Table 3

- This graph compares the 16 years of data of percentage change in the GDP during the period 2006 to 2022, I.e. the 8 years of data before and after 2006 demonetization has been compared and plotted on line graph to observe the changes in the GDP growth. From the above graph, out of 8 years, only 3 years data was showing higher growth than the before demonetization period. Rest of the 5 years, the growth was recorded lower than the before period.

4. Observations:

To understand the impact of demonetization on the Indian Economy with respect to the GDP value (in US Billion \$) from 1960 to 2023 is taken and applied the percentage change formula to the data and observed the following:

1. In the first period of demonetization i.e. in the year 1978, there was highest growth rate in the GDP in before the period of demonetization than the later date.
2. In the second period of demonetization i.e. in the year 2006 demonetization, there was huge volatility in GDP growth was found. It is very dangerous for any country to estimate the growth rate of GDPs for future periods and also to understand the economy progress.
3. In the third period of demonetization i.e. in the year 2014, there was high volatility in before period and less during the later period. It indicates that the later period was trying to stabilize the growth rate. However, there is no much positive impact on the demonetization.

5. Conclusion and Future scope of the study:

To conclude, the observation during the research say that, there may be other internal factors impacting the GDP growth rather the demonetization. The aim of demonetization of each period may not be justified for the purpose and had to be measure the impact on other factors like digitization of currency, terror activities, inflation, impact on sectors such as unorganized sector, real estate etc.

6. References:

1. Reserve Bank of India's official disclosures.
2. World bank data catalogue.
3. "7 years of demonetization: Change in use of cash in Indian economy", Business Standard, February 14, 2024.
4. Aggarwal M., & Gupta M. (2019). Demonetization: Move towards cash less economy. Finance India, 33(3), 639–654.
5. P. Bagya Lakshmi, Demonetization and LPG Reforms in Indian Economy, Rathinam Journal of Management (Rjm), Volume 11, Issue 2, March-May 2020, 18-22.
6. SomSekhar Bhattacharyy and Praveen Nemaana, "Effect of Demonetization on Advertising, Research & Development and Human Resource Intensities and its Impact on Firm's Performance", Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective, Sept 2021.
7. The "Rs 2000 note withdrawn: What happens if you fail to deposit, exchange it by September 30, 2023?", The times of India, May 23, 2023.
8. Wentao Wu a, Zhilu Lin a, Pejvak Oghazi b c, Pankaj C. Patel, The impact of demonetization on microfinance institutions, Journal of Business Research, Volume 153, December 2022, Pages 1-18